

COMPARISON OF THE CATAPHORETIC AND ELECTRO-OSMOTIC METHODS OF MEASURING ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL.

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The electrokinetic potential of a number of suspensions has been measured by the cataphoretic and the electro-osmotic methods and the results obtained by the two methods have been found to agree between themselves.

It follows from theory that the electrokinetic potential of a given colloidal system should be the same whether it is measured by the cataphoretic method or by the electro-osmotic method. The velocity of electro-osmosis, U , is connected with the electrokinetic potential, e , of the capillary wall by the equation

$$U = C_1 \frac{qe_1 ED}{\eta}$$

deduced by Smoluchowski, Perrin and Debye and Hückel, where $C_1 = 1/4\pi$, e , the electrokinetic potential of the capillary wall, E , the potential gradient, D , the viscosity of the dispersion medium and q , the cross section of the capillary. The cataphoretic velocity, V of a particle suspended in a liquid is given by the equation

$$V = C_2 \frac{e_2 ED}{\eta}$$

where $C_2 = 1/4\pi$ according to Smoluchowski, but according to Hückel it may be $1/4\pi$ or $1/6\pi$ depending on whether the particle is cylindrical or spherical in shape. The other terms have the same significance as in the case of electro-osmosis. For a given system U/V should, therefore, be unity according to Smoluchowski's equation and 1.5 according to Hückel's equations, provided the particles are spherical. This point has been subjected to experimental test by van der Grinten (*J. chim. phys.*, 1926, **23**, 209), by Henry (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A**, **133**, 106) and by Bull and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 111). Van der Grinten using a microcataphoretic cell of glass and particles formed of the same glass of which the cell is made, measured the cataphoretic velocity, V , of the particles and also the velocity of electro-osmosis of water, U , in the cell due to the electric charge of the cell wall. He obtained for U/V the value

1'5. His results have, however, been adversely criticised on the ground that the glass particles prepared by grinding have not the same surface as that of the cell. To overcome this difficulty Bull and Gortner suspended the glass particles in a dilute protein solution and measured U and V in a microcataphoretic cell of glass. They assumed that the surfaces of the cell and those of the particles were uniformly coated with a film of protein. Under these conditions they found U/V to be approximately equal to 1. Henry (*loc. cit.*) in his experiments, used spherical wax particles and coated the surface of the cataphoretic cell with the same wax. He also found U/V to be nearly equal to unity. In all these experiments the assumption is made that as a result of the wax or protein coating the surface structure of the particles has become identical with that of the cataphoretic cell. It is doubtful how far such an assumption is correct. This doubtful factor can, however, be eliminated if a porous diaphragm is prepared of the same particles, the cataphoretic velocity of which is being measured and U , the electro-osmotic velocity is determined by making use of this diaphragm. This procedure has been adopted in our experiments. The values of U and V were determined for particles of kaolin, kaolin coated with gelatin, silica, silica coated with fibrin, arsenious sulphide, etc. in contact with solutions of various electrolytes. The results obtained so far are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The kaolin or silica particles used in these experiments were prepared by allowing their aqueous suspensions about 6 inches in depth to stand in glass bottles and collecting the particles which settle to the bottom between two and four hours. The particles were coated with proteins, when desired, by shaking them with dilute solutions of proteins, removing the

FIG. 1.

supernatant solution after the sedimentation of the particles and shaking them again with fresh solutions of proteins and so on until their surface was saturated. The arsenious sulphide particles used were obtained by treating an arsenious sulphide solution with electrolytes of such concentration that the coagulation of the solution occurred in about three hours.

The arrangements used for the electro-osmotic experiments were similar to that used by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732) and also by Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2693). It consisted of a U-shaped tube, the side tubes of which were connected with a narrow tube bent four times at right angles, through two three-way glass stop-cocks (Fig. 1). The lower part of the U-tube was packed with the material which formed the diaphragm. The upper part of the U-tube and the bent tube were filled with solutions of electrolytes with which the particles forming the diaphragm were previously kept in contact for a time sufficiently long for the attainment of adsorption equilibrium. The bent tube connected with the U-tube contained an air-bubble in the middle. From a measurement of the movement of this air-bubble, when the electric field is applied, the volume of the liquid flowing through the diaphragm per second can be calculated, provided the diameter of the bore of the bent tube is known. In the equation

$$U = C_1 \frac{q e_1 E D}{\eta},$$

q represents the cross section of the capillary tube. If instead of a single capillary tube a porous diaphragm is used, we may regard it as a bundle of capillaries of effective cross section q . Now $E = i_1 R$, where i_1 is the current and R the resistance per unit length of the capillaries. Hence $R = \frac{l}{qk}$ where k is the specific conductivity of the liquid filling the pores of the diaphragm. Substituting this value of E in the above equation we get

$$U = C_1 \frac{i_1 e_1 D}{\eta k} \quad \text{or} \quad U/i_1 = C_1 \frac{e_1 D}{\eta k} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The cataphoretic velocities of the particles were determined in a micro-cataphoretic cell of the flat rectangular type used by Freundlich and Abramson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 128, 25) and by Chopra and Chaudhury (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1932, 19, 1115) with this modification that it was provided with two detachable side-tubes, one on each side. The joints were carefully ground so as to be leak-proof. Each side-tube carried an electrode vessel and a three-way stop-cock. The cell was cleaned thoroughly before use and then filled with the desired suspension, care being taken to remove all air-bubbles from the apparatus. Reversible electrodes

were placed in the electrode vessels and just before taking actual reading they were connected with the 220 volt lighting circuit through a sensitive milliammeter and an adjustable resistance. The milliammeter indicated the current which flowed through the system. The velocity of the particles were measured at two depths $d/6$ and $d/2$ respectively inside the cell, where d represents the depth of the cell. The value of d for the cell, used by us was 0.09 cm. The actual velocity of the particles was calculated from the formula,

$$V = \left(\frac{2}{3}V_1 + \frac{1}{3}V_2\right),$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the observed velocities at depths $d/6$ and $d/2$ respectively inside the cell as already stated. Now V is related to the electrokinetic potential by the equation,

$$V = \frac{C_2 e_2 D E}{\eta} = \frac{C_2 e_2 D i_2}{\eta A k} \quad \dots (2)$$

Since $E = i_1 R$, where i_2 is the current and R , the resistance per unit length of the cataphoretic cell and since $R = i_2 / A k$ where A is the cross sectional area of the cataphoretic cell and k , the specific conductivity of the suspension filling it.

Hence from equation (2) we get

$$\frac{V A}{i_2} = \frac{C_2 e_2 D}{\eta k} \quad \dots (3)$$

From equations (1) and (3) it follows that for the same suspension for which D , η and k have identical values

$$\frac{(V A)}{i_2} / (U/i_1) = \frac{C_2}{C_1} \cdot \frac{e_2}{e_1} \quad \dots (4)$$

TABLE I.

The cross sectional area 'A' of the cataphoretic cell = 0.09 sq. cm.

Material used.	Specific conductivity.	Current in milliamperes i_2 .	$V.A$ i_2	Current in milliamperes i_1 .	U/i_1 .	$\frac{e_2}{e_1} \times \frac{C_2}{C_1}$
Kaolin treated with HCl of diff. conc.	3.9×10^{-3}	3.25	0.0369	14	0.379	0.97
	1.05×10^{-3}	1.05	0.227	6	0.207	1.09
Gelatin coated kaolin and HCl of diff. conc.	1.03×10^{-1}	11.5	0.0305	10	0.028	1.09
	3.22×10^{-3}	3.00	0.0321	14	0.029	1.11
Silica and HCl of diff. conc.	7.74×10^{-3}	4.5	0.0182	10	0.0226	0.81
	1.19×10^{-3}	1.1	0.187	11	0.182	1.03
Fibrin coated silica and HCl of diff. conc.	1.6×10^{-3}	1.5	0.170	12	0.142	1.19
	3.2×10^{-4}	0.72	0.318	7	0.282	1.13
Arsenious sulphide treated with BaCl ₂ soln.	2.5×10^{-4}	0.7	0.401	3	0.407	0.99
CaCl ₂ soln.	3.4×10^{-4}	0.6	0.535	7.3	0.492	1.09
						Mean 1.05

It appears from the data recorded in Table I that the value of $C_2 e_2 / C_1 e_1$ is unity within the limits of experimental error. If it be assumed that $e_2 = e_1$ then it follows from our results that within the limits of experimental error $c_2 = c_1 = 1/4\pi$ i.e. C_2 as required by Smoluchowski's equation is independent of the shape of the particles. The assumption that $e_2 = e_1$ is justifiable since the same suspensions were used in the cataphoretic and electro-osmotic measurements. This result is useful in view of the fact that it demonstrates the reliability, provided proper precautions are taken of electro-osmotic method of measuring the electrokinetic potential of particles which settle quickly from their suspensions, thereby rendering the cataphoretic method of measuring electrokinetic potential rather difficult in their case. It may be mentioned here that in evaluating the electrokinetic potential from the experimental data, it has been assumed by us that the specific conductivity 'k' of the electrolyte solution within the pores of the diaphragm is identical with its specific conductivity in bulk, in other words, the effect due to surface conduction inside the pores is negligible. This assumption seems justifiable in view of the fact that the solutions used by us were fairly strongly conducting and the diameters of the pores were large, owing to the comparatively loose packing of the material forming the diaphragm.